

Stress Levels and Self- Management Strategies Among Senior Female Civil Servants in Ondo State

AUTHOR(S): AGUNBIADE, Rashida Bolanle (B.Ed, M.Ed),
OLUWASEYI, Omobola (RN, M.Sc.)
AND
ATANDERO, Margaret Oluronke (RN, M.Sc.)

Abstract

This study assessed the relationship between stress levels and self- management strategies among senior female civil servants in Ondo State. The study adopted Health Belief Model in explaining the disposition of women as civil servants and wives in paying attention to their health. The study adopted the descriptive research design of the survey type. The population of the study comprised all the 1245 senior female civil servants in Ondo State. The sample for this study was 312 (25%) respondents through multi-stage sampling procedure. The research instrument used was self – constructed questionnaire. Frequency counts, percentages, mean, and standard deviation and inferential statistics involving Pearson Product Moment Correlation were used to test the hypotheses. All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that the stress level prevalent among senior female civil servants in Ondo State was moderate. The study also showed that physiological, behavioral and psychological symptoms were significantly related to stress levels. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that efforts should be made by senior female civil servants to adopt appropriate strategies for effective management of stress through the use of regular exercise, relaxation, and adequate time - management to improve wellbeing.

Keywords: Stress, Stress Levels, Senior Female Civil Servants, Self-Management Strategies,

CJAR

Accepted 18 May 2021
Published 20 May 2021
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4775726

About Author

Author(s):

AGUNBIADE, Rashida Bolanle (B.Ed, M.Ed)
Counselling and Human Development Unit,
University of Medical Sciences, Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria.

OLUWASEYI, Omobola (RN, M.Sc.)
Faculty of Nursing,
University of Medical Sciences, Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria.

And

ATANDERO, Margaret Oluronke (RN, M.Sc.)
Faculty of Nursing,
University of Medical Sciences, Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria.

Introduction

Women play an important role in the decision making process in the family and organizations. Culture places women as the caretaker of the family. As wives, their main roles are to manage the family, care for, clean and maintain the home educate the children, cook and store food, buy goods. A woman in the home is called a housewife, and outside the home, she is referred to as a working woman because she goes to work, and earns salary/wages. In both situations, the woman is working. With globalization, civilization and improvement in education, women's literacy rate seems to be increasing; this has resulted in more women taking up jobs. Working in and outside the home are two phases of a woman's life. Balancing government work and family life appears to be a major hurdle for women resulting in dealing with an increasing stress levels. The problem of combining official or government work with other forms of task appears to have pushed many women to fatigue, frustration, anger, the use of drugs and becoming 'burnout' that is, a prolonged response to chronic emotional and interpersonal stressors on the job (Maslach, et al, 2000).

Worldwide, it appears women are indispensable group in the nation's development as they have great abilities needed to evolve a new economic order, to improve social and political development and consequently transform the society in to a better one; yet they are faced with a lot of expectations from the society so much that Ezeigbo (1996) stated that most Nigerian women labour under stress because they are overburdened by the responsibilities in their lives, those established by the society and themselves as they are expected to perform their traditional roles efficiently, run their homes, be good wives and step-mother. They are also expected to add to the family income, cater for the extended family members and perform efficiently as administrative officers in the place of work.

There are diverse source of stress for women especially for those in the administrative cadre. These sources are categorized as those caused by the demands of the job (work related) such as heavy work load, unclear work roles, time pressure, emotional demands of work performance pressure, conflict at work, and those caused by personal vulnerability of women (non-work related). All these seem to be related with increased stress and the outcome of these are physical problem, mental health problem, reduction in the quality of productivity indolence, reduction in the quality of output, and absenteeism which is a situation where the worker is present at work, but feels too ill to work effectively and efficiently (Tenibiaje, 2013).

Today, important changes appear to be happening and the role of a woman is being constantly redefined as she now engages in several roles that are beyond the traditional ones. Women who in the past have had to perform their motherly roles on full time now add their housewifery roles with the demands of holding administrative jobs. They no longer accept that women's place is only in the home.

This development appears to have made women, especially those in the senior cadre of Ondo State Civil Service to die their untimely probably because of build-up of untreated stress acquired from the struggle of meeting their dual roles as women more so that stress is an inevitable aspect of living from which there is no escape. It is pertinent to note that female workers in the Ondo State Civil Service especially those in the senior cadre at the administrative level between age 35- 59 from grade level 10 and above, married or divorced are more predisposed to stress due to some distinctiveness and problems of their workplace added with family role.

In view of the above, the study examined stress levels and self- management strategies among senior female civil servants in Ondo State. This study specifically:

1. examined stress levels among senior female civil servants in Ondo State; and

- investigated available strategies that senior female civil servants can adopt to reduce the effect of stress in and out of their workplace

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised for this study:

- What is the stress level prevalent among senior female civil servants in Ondo State?
- What are the self-management strategies used in reducing stress among senior female civil servants in Ondo State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were postulated for this study:

- There is no significant relationship between physiological symptoms and stress levels.
- There is no significant relationship between psychological symptoms and stress levels.
- There is no significant relationship between the use of self-management and stress levels.

Methodology

Descriptive research design of survey type was adopted for the study, the population for this study consisted of 1245 senior female civil servants from grade level 10 and above. Multi-stage sampling was adopted to select 312 respondents. A self-structured questionnaire titled 'Stress Levels and Self-Management Strategies Questionnaire' SLSMQ. It was subjected to screening by test and measurement expert and supervisor for face validity. The construct validity was ensured using scores obtained from the two measures were correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation and a correlation co-efficient of 0.73 was obtained. A reliability coefficient of 0.85 was obtained using a test-retest method and this was found to be significant at 0.05 level of significance. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation, bar chart and percentage to answer research questions. Inferential statistics were used to test the correlation between Stress level and Self – Management Strategies using Pearson Product Moment Correlation and t-test to test the hypotheses formulated at 0.05 level of significance

Results

Research Question 1: What is the stress level prevalent among senior female civil servants in Ondo State?

In analysing the question, scores on stress level prevalent among senior female civil servants in Ondo State were used. Mean score, frequency counts and percentages were used to illustrate the responses to items 8-30 in Section B of "Stress Levels and Self-management Strategies Questionnaire (SLSMSQ)". To determine the stress levels prevalent among senior female civil servants in Ondo State (low, moderate and high), the mean score and standard deviation of the responses on stress levels prevalent were used.

The low stress levels prevalent among senior female civil servants were determined by subtracting the standard deviation score from the mean score ($38.66-9.54=29.12$). The moderate stress levels prevalent among senior female civil servants was determined by the mean score of the responses on stress levels prevalent among senior female civil servants in Ondo State (38.66) while high level of stress levels prevalent among senior female civil servants was determined by adding the mean score and the standard deviation score of the responses on stress levels prevalent among senior female civil servants ($38.66+9.54=48.20$). Therefore, the low level of stress prevalent among senior female civil servants starts from 23.00 to 29.12; the moderate level starts from 29.13 to 48.19 while the high stress levels

prevalent among senior female civil servants starts from 48.20-69.00. The stress level prevalent among senior female civil servants in Ondo State is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Stress levels prevalent among senior female civil servants in Ondo State

Level of stress	Frequency	Percent
Low (23.00-29.02)	65	20.8
Moderate (29.03-48.29)	180	57.7
High (48.30-69.00)	67	21.5
Total	312	100.0

Table 1 presents the stress levels prevalent among senior female civil servants in Ondo State. The result showed that out of 312 senior female civil servants sampled, 65 representing 20.8% had low level of stress levels. Those who had moderate were 180 representing 57.7% while those with high level were 67 representing 21.5%. This showed that the level of stress levels prevalent among senior female civil servants in Ondo State was moderate. The stress level prevalent among senior female civil servants in Ondo State is further depicted in Figure i.

Figure i: Stress levels prevalent among senior female civil servants in Ondo State

Research Question 2: What are the self-management strategies used in reducing stress among senior female civil servants in Ondo State?

Table 2: Self-Management strategies adopted in reducing stress among senior female civil servants in Ondo State

S/N	ITEMS	YES		NO		MEAN	RANKING
		f	%	f	%		
1	I rarely take official work home.	152	48.7	160	51.3	1.49	8 th

2	I maintain regular exercise for fitness.	139	44.6	173	55.4	1.45	10 th
3	I practice relaxation techniques such as meditation, imagery, yoga jogging.	197	63.1	115	36.9	1.63	5 th
4	I manage time by setting goals for myself in measurable manner.	217	69.6	95	30.4	1.70	3 rd
5	I set priority for my daily schedule.	242	77.6	70	22.4	1.78	1 st
6	I organize my work orderly putting things in its right place for easy access.	223	71.5	89	28.5	1.71	2 nd
7	I limit connection to office via modem or technological devices after office hours.	167	53.5	145	46.5	1.54	7 th
8	I attend to unofficial discussion standing up.	144	46.2	168	53.8	1.46	9 th
9	I have a mentor, someone whom I share my frustration and challenges with.	215	68.9	97	31.1	1.69	4 th
10	I effectively use others in accomplishing work assignment.	182	58.3	130	41.7	1.58	6 th

Table 2 presents the self-management strategies adopted in reducing stress among senior female civil servants in Ondo State. The result reveals that 48.7% of the respondents rarely take official work home, 44.6% maintain regular exercise for fitness, 63.1% practice relaxation techniques such as meditation, imagery, yoga jogging, 69.6% manage time by setting goals in a measurable manner, 77.6% set priority for daily schedule, 71.5% organized work orderly putting things in its right place for easy access, 53.5% limit connection to office via modem or technological devices after office hours, 46.2% attend to unofficial discussion standing up, 68.9% have a mentor, someone to share frustration and challenges with while 58.3% effectively use others in accomplishing work assignment. However, the use of exercise had low percentage of 44.6% ranking 10th position. This implies that in a way, attention should be paid to it as this could be a factor for stress.

Using a cut off mean of 1.50 and above for the rating scale, only items 3,4, 5,6,7,9 and 10 had mean scores above the cut off mean. This implies that the use of relaxation techniques such as meditation, imagery, yoga, jogging, time management by setting goals in a measurable manner, setting priority for daily schedule, organizing work orderly putting things in its right place for easy access, limiting connection to office via modem or technological devices after office hours, having someone to share frustration and challenges with and effectively using others in accomplishing work assignment are self-management strategies adopted in reducing stress among senior female civil servants in Ondo State.

KEY:

- A: I rarely take official work home.
- B: I maintain regular exercise for fitness.
- C: I practice relaxation techniques such as meditation, imagery, yoga jogging.
- D: I manage time by setting goals for myself in measurable manner.
- E: I set priority for my daily schedule.
- F: I organize my work orderly putting things in its right place for easy access.
- G: I limit connection to office via modem or technological devices after office hours.
- H: I attend to unofficial discussion standing up.
- I: I have a mentor, someone whom I share my frustration and challenges with.
- J: I effectively use others in accomplishing work assignment.

Figure ii: Self-Management strategies adopted in reducing stress among senior female civil servants in Ondo State.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between physiological symptoms and stress levels.

In order to test the hypothesis, scores relating to physiological symptoms and stress levels were computed and subjected to statistical analysis involving Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Correlation analysis of physiological symptoms and stress levels

<i>Variables</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>r_{cal}</i>	<i>r_{Table}</i>
Physiological wellness	312	11.990	3.48	0.899*	0.088
Stress Level	312	38.673	9.65		

***p<0.05 (Significant Result)**

Table 3 shows that $r_{cal}(0.899)$ is greater than $r_{Table}(0.088)$ at 0.05 level of significance. The hypothesis is hereby rejected. This implies that there is significant relationship between physiological symptoms and stress levels.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between psychological symptoms and stress levels.

In order to test the hypothesis, scores relating to psychological symptoms and stress levels were computed and subjected to statistical analysis involving Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Correlation analysis of psychological symptoms and stress levels

<i>Variables</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>r_{cal}</i>	<i>r_{table}</i>
Psychological wellness	312	8.026	2.39	0.847*	0.088
Stress Level	312	38.673	9.65		

***p<0.05 (Significant Result)**

Table 4 shows that $r_{cal}(0.847)$ is greater than $r_{Table}(0.088)$ at 0.05 level of significance. The hypothesis is hereby rejected. This implies that there is significant relationship between psychological symptoms and stress levels.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between the use of self-management and stress levels.

In order to test the hypothesis, scores relating to self-management and stress levels were computed and subjected to statistical analysis involving Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 level of significance. The result is presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Correlation analysis of self- management and stress levels

<i>Variables</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>r_{cal}</i>	<i>r_{table}</i>
Self- management	312	16.022	2.36	0.899*	0.088
Stress Level	312	38.673	9.65		

***p<0.05 (Significant Result)**

Table 5 shows that $r_{cal}(0.899)$ is greater than $r_{table}(0.088)$ at 0.05 level of significance. The hypothesis is hereby rejected. This implies that there is significant relationship between self-management strategies and stress levels.

Discussion

The study showed that the stress level prevalent among senior female civil servants in Ondo State was moderate. This means that to some extent, according to the findings of this study, senior female civil servants are aware of stress reduction strategies. However, the study revealed that effective time management, prioritization of activities, goal setting, regular exercise and relaxation were self-management strategies adopted in reducing stress among senior female civil servants in Ondo State. The finding is consistent with the submission of Pettigrew (2003), that there is a close relationship between stress

management and time management. Yilmaz, Yoncalik and Bektas (2010) found that there is a positive significant relationship between time management behaviour and mental health improvement of students and teachers. Yilmaz, Yoncalik and Bektas (2010) explained that time management is the use of tools, techniques and principles to control time spent on low-priority needs and to ensure that time is invested in activities leading toward achieving desired, high-priority goals.

Bergen, Soper and Gaster (2002) reiterated that the premise behind self-management is that employees can and do take an active role in regulating their performance, which involve setting of goals, monitoring behavior that relates to those goals, and rewarding themselves for goal achievement. This was supported by Pettigrew (2003) who concluded that reasonable and achievable goals should be set both at short or long term range. Covey, Merrill and Merrill (2004) confirmed that setting priorities is an important strategy in self-management; it is to attend to those tasks that are important but not urgent. DauBenmier (2007) said that programme that focuses on good diet, exercise, making the physical health a priority, getting enough rest, and relaxation through the use of meditation, yoga or massage, improving communication and stress management are beneficial to human well-being.

It was found that there was significant relationship between physiological wellness and stress levels. This implies that symptoms like headache backache, insomnia, high blood pressure, weight loss are evidences of the presence of stress among female civil servants. This assertion was supported by Joanna and Katzman (2013) that tense muscles in the back of the neck and even in the scalp are used to describe stress related headaches. In the study conducted by Porkka-Heiskanen, Zitting and Wigren (2013), physiological symptoms such as insomnia or sleep disorder is very much related to stress. They said that although occasional disturbance in sleep belong to normal life, but chronic disturbance increase the risk for impaired function, development of somatic and mental disorders, and increased health care cost. Black (2015) opined that sleep disorder has been identified as a symptom of stress that affects the job productivity of employees in work place.

The study showed that there was significant relationship between psychological symptoms and stress levels. This implies that despite the moderate level of stress among senior female civil servants in Ondo State, there was a noticeable relationship between psychological symptoms and stress. Psychological problem such as moodiness, depression, loneliness can impair the health of women if not well managed. Nwokedi (2004) stated that depression can have a substantial effect on employee's work environment because it can interfere with their abilities to do their jobs effectively. This was supported by National Mental Health Association (2004) which observed that depression interfere with the ability to work, sleep, eat and think right.

The depressed individual experiences prolonged feelings of hopelessness and helplessness. They are unhappy with their life but feel that they are incapable of improving things.

A stressed individuals is intolerant of others even at the family level, leading to poor family interpersonal relationship. Good interpersonal relationship among family members could be a source of successful stress management among working women. Asarnow, Carlson and Guthrie (2010) stated that women whose family members live in harmony often experience little form of stress than those in disunity. To keep stress away, Gotlib et al (2012) in their study on family social support and stress management submitted that talking things out with family or friends or allowing them to help through a difficult time can help someone manage stress.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that stress level prevalent among senior female civil servants in Ondo State was moderate. Effective time management, prioritization of activities, organization and relaxation were self-management strategies adopted in reducing stress among senior female civil servants in Ondo State. However, response on regular exercise ranked tenth position, meaning that little or no time was spared for fitness as a result of overwhelming dual roles women are exposed to. Symptoms ranging from behavioural to psychological and physiological symptoms were indicators of stress level and wellness among female senior civil servants in Ondo State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- Concerted efforts should be made by senior female civil servants to adopt appropriate strategies for effective management of stress, so as to improve general wellbeing.
- Senior female civil servants should ensure effective time management by setting measurable goals to enhance wellness.
- Senior female civil servant should prioritize their daily schedule of activities in order to reduce stress to manageable level.
- Government should ensure better and stress-free working environment for senior female civil servants through provision of conducive working environment in order to reduce stress.
- Senior civil servants should endeavour to practice relaxation techniques such as mediation, imagery, yoga jogging and physical exercise in order to reduce stress.

References

- Asarnow, J. R., Carlson, G. A., & Guthrie, D. (1987). Coping strategies, self-perceptions, hopelessness, and perceived family environments in depressed and suicidal children. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 55(3), 361-366.
- Black, D. S., Gilian, A., O'Reilly, B. S. and Irwin, R. M. (2015). Mindfulness meditation and improvement in sleep quality and daytime impairment among older adults with sleep disturbances. *Journal of American Medical Association. Internal Medicine* 175(4), 494-501.
- Covey, S. R., Merrill, A. R., & Merrill, R. R. (2004). *First things first: To love, to learn, to leave a legacy*. New York: Simon & Schuster.
- Dau- Benmier, J. J. (2007). The contribution of changes in diet, exercise, and stress management to changes in coronary risk in women and men in the multisite cardiac. Lifestyle Intervention Program. *Annals of Behavioural Medicine*, 33(1), 57-68.
- Ezeigbo, T. A. (1996). *Gender issues in Nigeria: A feminine perspective*. Lagos, Nigeria: Vista Books
- Gotlib, I. H., Krasnoperova, E., Neubauer, D. L. & Joormann, J. (2012). Attentional biases for negative interpersonal stimuli in clinical depression. *Journal of Abnormal Psychology*, 113, 127-135.

- Joanna, G., & Katzman, M. D., (2013). *Headache: Clinical Syndromes, Pathophysiology and Management*. University of Mexico: Health Sciences Center.
- Maslach, C., Schanfeld, W., Leiter, M. (2000). Job burnout inventory. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 52, 397-422.
- National Mental Health Association (2004). Depression is a workplace barrier for working women. Available at: <http://www.Prnewswire.com>
- Nwokedi, S. A. (2004). *Strategies for improving workers conditions*. Owerri: Joe Mankpa Publishers.
- Pettigrew, A. C. (2003). Self-management: Stress and time. In P. S. Yoder-Wise, *Leading and managing in nursing*, 3rd ed. (pp. 413-430). St. Louis: Mosby.
- Porkka-Heiskanen, T., Zitting, K. M. & Wigren, H. K. (2013). Sleep, its regulation and possible mechanisms of sleep disturbances. *Acta Physiologica*, 208(4), 311-328. .
- Tenibiaje, D. J. (2013). Work related stress. *European Journal of Business and Social Science*, 1(10), 73-80
- Yilmaz, I., Yoncalik, O., & Bektas, F. (2010). Relationship between time management behavior and academic success. *Journal of New World Sciences Academy*, 5, 187-194.

Cite this article:

Author(s), AGUNBIADE, Rashida Bolanle (B.Ed, M.Ed), OLUWASEYI, Omobola (RN, M.Sc.), ATANDERO, Margaret Oluronke (RN, M.Sc.), (2021). "Stress Levels and Self-Management Strategies Among Senior Female Civil Servants in Ondo State". **Name of the Journal**: Commonwealth Journal of Academic Research, (CJAR.EU), P, 26- 36. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4775726> , Issue: 5, Vol.: 2, Article: 4, Month: May, Year: 2021. Retrieved from <https://www.cjar.eu/all-issues/>

Published by

AND

ThoughtWares Consulting & Multi Services International (TWCMSI)

